

THE IMPACT OF INNOVATION PROJECTS ON THE EFFICIENCY OF THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY

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Abstract

This research aims to study the impact of innovation projects applied in the oil and gas industry on the development of this sector. This research is of great importance for Azerbaijan because our country has rich oil and gas fields. The purpose of the study is to review innovation projects that allow increasing the efficiency of the oil and gas industry in the country.

The article envisages the implementation of innovation projects such as a new oil strategy for the efficient use of the country's oil and gas resources. Scientific research on the application of innovation technologies as innovation projects is carried out. This is important for increasing the efficiency of the oil and gas industry.

The purpose of the article is to examine the importance of calculations to determine the impact of implementing innovation projects in the oil and gas industry.

Keywords: innovation, innovation projects, oil and gas industry, efficiency, new oil strategy.

I. Introduction (*Heading 1*)

The future of the oil and gas industry depends on the implementation of many scientific and technical development and innovations. Sustainable development of companies in the long term is determined by their ability to predict and flexibly respond to changing conditions of the external environment, to maintain and acquire new competitive advantages in the markets, including the oil and gas resources market.

Currently, all companies concerned with finding additional sources of competitive advantages [1]. The leading roles are played by factors that provide dynamic advantages (innovative processes, advantages of an earlier start of production, the need to improve production, etc.), and, conversely, those that determine static advantages (prices for raw materials and resources, the size of the domestic market, etc.) cease to play a key role.

In this regard, the role of managing the scientific and technical potential of a company increases, which should be focused on the long-term goals of its technological development.

The peculiarity of the oil and gas industry Azerbaijan is that mining is carried out on the sea. Therefore, this feature must be taken into account when defining innovation policy.

Managing innovation projects to maximize the market the market capitalization of enterprises.

The concept of cost management assumes that all management decisions are mainly aimed not at obtaining profits in the near future, but at obtaining much greater profits and income in the future [2]. In real management practice, specific investment and innovation projects related to the development of so-called product and process innovations can influence the increase in the market value of a company (enterprise).

Product innovations are usually aimed at producing new types of products (goods, services). Technological innovations are associated with the creation, development and implementation of new technological processes and new types of equipment. They are the ones that can bring additional profits to the company and increase cash flows as a result of introducing new products to the market, improving the quality of previously manufactured products and reducing the cost of production. But they, being quite expensive, can cause huge losses to the enterprise due to scientific and technical errors, and the greater the losses, the more radically new products or processes are created and developed. One of the important issues in the problem of innovations is the assessment of the contribution specific innovations to increasing the value of an enterprise or company. In this case, innovations are investment projects, the main difference of which from traditional investment projects is that here they should be considered as a process of creating and mastering in production and marketing new and improved quality types of products, technological process and equipment [3].

It is advisable to assess the contribution of innovation to increasing the value of an enterprise using the discounted cash flow method. The justified market value of an enterprise C_{max} is possible without and with the introduction of an innovation. In the case of the absence of an innovation, the justified market value of the enterprise will be equal to the current value of the expected income (possible losses) of the enterprise with a simple continuation of its operations, i.e. the value of the enterprise without the introduction of an innovation $C_{no\ innovations}$:

$$C_{max} = C_{no\ innovations} = \sum_{t=1}^T CF_t / (1+r)^t \quad (1)$$

CF_t – annual future cash flows;

r – discount rate.

In the case of innovation implementation, the enterprise value will be:

$$C_{max} = C_{no\ innovations} + NPV_i, \quad (2)$$

where NPV_i is the net present value created by the innovation.

As the innovation project is implemented in accordance with its life cycle, the market value of the enterprise changes by the amount of net present value (NPV).

The increase in the market value of the enterprise will depend on the competitive advantages of a particular innovation project being implemented [4]. Enterprise innovation management should primarily consist of the fact that as the relevant innovation project progresses through the stages, the estimated market value of the enterprise continues to increase. If it turns out that the estimated market value of the enterprise as a result of the project implementation beings to decrease rather than increase, then the business plan of the project should be immediately adjusted [5].

In the process of implementing an innovation project, two parameters should be constantly monitored:

C- factor – the ratio between the estimated market value of the enterprise with and without innovation.

Δ is the difference between the internal rate of return of the project (IRR) and the weighted average cost of capital of the enterprise WACC. Then the factor is expressed as follows:

$$\Delta = IRR - WACC, \quad (3)$$

The boundary values of the given parameters are: for the factor C – one, for the difference Δ – zero.

In other words, when the estimated market value of the enterprise, which has changed as a result of the implementation of innovative projects, exceeds their value without the implementation of the projects and when internal rate of return of the project continues to exceed the weighted average cost of capital of the enterprise WACC, the innovative project actually increases its value.

When the C factor becomes less than one, and the parameter falls below zero, the value of the enterprise implementing the project decreases due to the continuation of this project.

If the parameters C and are in different directions, i.e. at a given point in time a) factor $C > 1$, and < 0 or vice versa: b) factor $C < 1$ with > 0 , then in this case nothing definite can be said about the change in the value of the enterprise, it is only recommended to put the project under special control. When assessing and making innovative decisions, the project analysis method should be used [6]. However, investment projects of an innovative nature differ from simple investment projects. For an innovative project, in contrast to an ordinary investment project, continuous improvement is characteristic at all stages of innovative activity: improving the quality of innovative products, improving technological processes and organizational structures [7].

If the innovation project under consideration satisfies the level of indicators for the compliance groups, the next step is to evaluate its economic and financial efficiency.

The following are usually used as the main economic criteria for evaluating innovations:

1. Net present value, NPV (net present value, NPV);
2. Internal rate of return of the project, IRR;
3. Discounted payback period of the project;
4. Profitability index, PI;
5. The ratio of discounted benefits to discounted costs (benefits/ costs).

It should be noted that during the period of research and development (R&D), the costs incurred do not provide useful income and profit and therefor are lost until the start of the innovation implementation and profit generation. However, this circumstance is usually not taken into account when calculating the main indicators of the economic efficiency of an innovation project using traditional methods [8].

In this regard, it is proposed to adjust the current formula of net present value (NPV) for a single innovation project taking this aspect into account as follows:

$$NPV_{ip} = \sum_{t=1}^T (B_t - (K_{rd} + O_t) - TP_t) / (1+r)^{(t-t_0)} - \sum_{t=1}^T K_{rd} / (1+r)^{(t-t_0)}, \quad (4)$$

where B_t are the benefits of the innovation project in the year; K_t are capital investments in the innovation; K_{rd} are R&D costs; O_t are operating costs; TP_t are tax payments; r is the discount rate; T is the life of the innovation project; t_0 is the year of the beginning of the innovation implementation and the receipt of profit.

When using this formula, R&D costs incurred before the beginning of the innovation implementation and the receipt of profit are reduced to the first year of the beginning of the implementation by dividing by the discount coefficient to the appropriate degree, and those incurred after the beginning of the implementation – by multiplying by the appropriate discount factor. Cash receipts after the implementation of the innovation are also given to the moment of the start of implementation, and not to the beginning of the life cycle of the innovation project.

Conclusion:

1. The main problems of scientific and technical development of the oil and gas industry are:

increasing the efficiency of geological exploration and the formation of a raw material base that ensures the implementation of long-time development plans:

increasing the efficiency of developing fields with hard-to-recover reserves;

increasing the efficiency of oil and gas condensate extraction;

increasing the potential productivity of medium- and low-flow wells, both at the construction stage and at the operation stage;

involving additional volumes of gas and condensate in deep processing to obtain motor fuels, synthetic liquid hydrocarbons and other products.

2. The development of an innovative strategy for a company should be based on the existing theoretical foundations of innovative management. It is important to use the accumulated experience of conducting similar studies in the country and abroad, which is a prerequisite for a complete solution to the problems of selecting priority technological problems.

3. In a market economy, one of the important elements of management theory and practice is enterprise value management, which should be aimed at ensuring

growth in market value. As an innovative project is implemented in accordance with its life cycle, the market value of the enterprise changes by the amount of net present value. This increase will depend on the competitive advantages of a particular innovative project.

4. Innovative investment projects have features that must be taken into account when assessing their effectiveness. If, when analyzing traditional investment projects, one can limit oneself to standards and developed methods, then in the presence of innovative projects, a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods and a comparative variant analysis is required.

5. The choice of an innovative solution should be made not only based on the results of an assessment of economic efficiency, but also taking into account the risk of their implementation. It is necessary to take into account that the research and development (R&D) stage of the life cycle of an innovative project is characterized by a particularly high level of risk.

6. The specifics of innovative activity involve the use of both economic assessment and consideration of various criteria, each of which may be decisive in the decision-making process regarding the implementation of the project. The paper proposes a structure of groups and indicators of the compliance of an innovation with its innovative purpose. If the innovation project under consideration satisfies the level of indicators for compliance groups, the next stage is the assessment of its economic and financial efficiency.

7. When developing a methodology for assessing the efficiency of innovative solution, it is necessary to take into account the structure of the project life cycle. In particular, at the stage of R&D the costs incurred do not provide for the receipt of useful income and profit

and are lost until the start of the implementation of the innovation and the receipt of profit, which requires an adjustment of the net present value (NPV) indicator.

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